

THE CIRCULATION AND WATER LEVEL FORECAST ATLAS:
A NEW PRODUCT IN DEVELOPMENT AT NOS

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ABSTRACT

The National Ocean Service (NOS) is developing a new product aimed at improving the prediction of water level and currents in key waterways of the United States. The Circulation and Water Level Forecast Atlas will provide a series of charts and graphs for predicting the tide and tidal current anywhere in a particular estuary, and for providing information on the effects of wind, barometric pressure, and river discharge.

The atlas will be produced using a numerical hydrodynamic model implemented for a particular estuary using an extensive oceanographic and meteorological data set. The atlas will represent the circulation at many more locations than the traditional NOS "Tidal Current Charts," which represent currents only at those locations where current data have been obtained and analyzed. The additional locations will include those of special navigational or environmental interest where current measurements cannot be made using traditional moored current meters. The additional spatial coverage resulting from the use of a numerical model will be especially evident in the atlas' tidal height charts, which will depict the changing water level over the entire waterway for each hour of the tidal cycle. On each chart coheight lines will traverse the entire waterway; tide predictions will no longer be limited to a few coastal locations.

Use of a numerical hydrodynamical model, combined with the results of statistical data analyses, will also allow the synthesis of important meteorological and river effects in a way that will permit factors be applied to the tide or tidal current prediction based on wind, pressure, or river discharge information available to a user. In a waterway where NOS real-time water level gages are in operation, the atlas will supplement the NOS data retrieval software package called TIDES ABC, by providing a means to extrapolate the real-time data from these gages to other locations in the waterway.

The first Circulation and Water Level Forecast Atlas is planned for Delaware River and Bay, where NOS conducted a 2 1/2-year circulation survey. The observations from that survey will be used to implement and assess the skill of the high-resolution numerical model that will be used to produce the atlas.

1. INTRODUCTION

The accurate forecasting of water levels and currents is important to pilots, commercial shippers, fishermen, the Coast Guard, the Navy, and others in the marine community. At the present time, our ability to fulfill this need is limited to prediction of the tidal portion of the change in water level or current at only those specific locations where water level or current data have been obtained. Such tidal prediction is based on classical harmonic analysis techniques and, when meteorology and river flow are not factors, can be quite accurate, the technique being based on known astronomical periods of the relative motions of the earth, moon, and sun. Such predictions are presented in tide tables, tidal current tables, and tidal current charts published by the National Ocean Service (NOS) in NOAA.

2. PROBLEMS IN FORECASTING
WATER LEVEL AND CIRCULATION

One problem with our present capability is that we cannot accurately predict water level changes or currents resulting from the effects of wind, barometric pressure, and river discharge. In an area such as the Gulf of Mexico, these meteorological effects can totally dominate the tidal effects. But even in areas where the tide usually dominates, such as in the estuaries of the East Coast of the United States, the meteorologically induced changes can be very important to certain members of the marine community. For example, for a pilot bringing into port a large oil tanker whose draft is of the same order as the channel depth, a reduction in water level due to the wind could force him to wait several hours outside the bay.

Another problem with our present capability is that there are often requirements

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for water level or current predictions at locations where data were never collected. This leaves the user to improvise his own interpolation technique, which in many cases is not likely to produce accurate results, especially for currents. Currents can vary dramatically from location to location because of changes in bathymetry or irregular shorelines. Current meters on moorings cannot be put in navigation channels because they would be hit by ships. Nor can they be deployed at all locations of potential interest because of the cost. Tide gages are rarely installed in the middle of bays, thus limiting tide predictions to a few points along the coast.

3. APPROACHES TO THE PROBLEM

One approach to the problem of forecasting the water level changes or currents caused by the wind, river discharge and other nontidal forces, is the implementation of real-time data systems¹. Such systems provide actual water level heights or current speeds and directions, for immediate use or as a basis for a short-term forecast. NOS presently has 17 real-time water level gages in operation around the country, accessible from any IBM-compatible microcomputer using a software package called TIDES ABC. NOS also has installed real-time current stations in Miami Harbor, Delaware Bay, and Charleston Harbor.

An approach to the problem of tidal prediction being limited to only a few locations where data have been obtained is the use of a numerical hydrodynamic model. Such a model, once validated by careful comparison with observed water level and current data, can provide predictions at locations where data have not been obtained. The quality of such predictions from today's best models are probably accurate enough for tidal heights. Tidal current predictions from numerical models present more problems but appear to have reached a state amenable to practical application. NOS has implemented numerical models for several estuaries, including the Delaware Bay, Columbia River, and Miami Harbor.

Both of the above approaches came together in the NOS Delaware River and Bay project. An experimental system was established in which a numerical model was run in real-time, driven by real-time water level and meteorological data from the field. This model was updated hourly and was also run twice a day in a 36-hour forecast mode utilizing forecast wind data from the Limited Fine Mesh weather model of the National Weather Service². Predicted values were checked using data

from other real-time water level gages along the estuary as well as from a real-time current station (installed with a remote acoustic Doppler sensor, RADS).

Another approach to both the problem of forecasting nontidal changes in water level and currents and the problem of insufficient spatial coverage also makes use of a numerical hydrodynamical model and is the subject of this paper. This approach is to produce a model-generated product called a Circulation and Water Level Forecast Atlas. This atlas will provide graphical techniques for predicting the water levels and currents anywhere in a particular waterway, including the effects of the tide, wind, barometric pressure, and river discharge.

4. DESIGN OF THE CIRCULATION AND WATER LEVEL FORECAST ATLAS

The atlas will have two major parts, one dealing with tidal phenomena and one dealing with nontidal phenomena. An actual prototype, using model-generated output, has been produced for the tidal part, and thus is further along in development than the nontidal part. This prototype was produced for the Delaware River and Bay because NOS already had a model for that area as well as detailed oceanographic data from a recent 2 1/2-year NOS circulation survey. The sections of the prototype tidal part and the proposed sections of the nontidal part are briefly described below.

4.1 Tidal Circulation and Height Charts

Tidal Circulation Charts show the speeds and directions of the tidal current for each hour of an average tidal cycle. They present a comprehensive view of the tidal circulation of an entire waterway, and provide a means for determining the speed and direction of the tidal current for any time at numerous locations throughout that waterway. The direction of the current at each location is indicated by an arrow and the speed is indicated by a figure in the center of the arrow (see Figure 1). These charts are similar to the "Tidal Current Charts" that NOS has published for 12 waterways in the U.S., except that, on the tidal current charts, current vectors were depicted only at locations where actual measurements had been made. The model-produced Tidal Circulation Charts have many more locations represented. The current depicted at each location is the average tidal flow over the entire water depth for that hour of the tidal cycle. No meteorological or river flow

Figure 1. Sample tidal circulation chart (See text for explanation).

effects are included in the flows shown on this set of charts.

In the Delaware River and Bay prototype, there are 13 charts, beginning with the chart representing the flow at the time of high water at the reference tide station, Breakwater Harbor, Delaware, and followed by charts representing the flow at each subsequent hour. The speeds shown on these charts represent an average situation. However, the tidal current varies from day to day, principally in accordance with the phase, parallax, and declination of the moon. Therefore, to obtain speeds for a particular day and hour, the speeds shown on the charts must be adjusted using a table provided in the atlas and the daily tide predictions at Breakwater Harbor, Delaware, also provided in the atlas.

The atlas also includes an analogous but completely new product -- Tidal Height Charts. These charts graphically display the varying water levels over an entire waterway for each hour of the tidal cycle. Because these charts are model-generated, tidal water level predictions

are no longer limited to a few coastal locations. Instead, coheight contours traverse the entire bay and represent the effects of changing bathymetry on the tide in mid-bay.

Tidal Height Charts show the height of the tide above chart datum (Mean Low Water or Mean Lower Low Water) in a waterway for each hour of an average tidal cycle. They present a comprehensive view of the tide for the entire waterway and provide a means for determining the height of the tide for any time at numerous locations throughout that waterway. The height of the tide is represented in three ways on each chart (see Figure 2). First, the spatial variation in tidal heights throughout the bay and river is depicted using coheight contours at 0.2 foot intervals. Second, the heights at a few selected points are represented by a histogram within a circle near each point. Also shown within that circle are three horizontal lines: the lower line represents mean low water; the middle line represents mean tide level; and the upper line represents mean high water at that location. An "F" to the right of the mean tide level line indicates that the tide is falling, while an "R" indicates that the tide is rising. The value of mean tide level is shown to the left of that line. The height value for that hour of the tidal cycle is shown just above the histogram. The third way in which tidal height is displayed is in an inset showing the water level for that hour of the tidal cycle along the main navigation channel. This plot also shows the variation of mean high water along the shipping channel, as well as the variation of mean tide level.

In the Delaware River and Bay prototype there are 13 Tidal Height Charts, for the same hours of the tidal cycle as for the Tidal Circulation Charts. To obtain tidal heights for a particular day and hour, the heights must also be adjusted using the Breakwater Harbor predictions, the table mentioned above, and the mean tide level figures within the circular symbols on the charts.

The Tidal Corange Chart shows the variation in mean tidal range over the entire waterway, using contours at 0.25 foot intervals. The variation in mean tidal range up the waterway, along the navigational channel, is shown in the inset. The two Cotidal Charts show the change in the times of high water and low water, respectively, along the waterway. The insets shows how long it takes high or low water to travel up the waterway along the navigation channel. All times are in hours after the time of high water at the

Figure 2. Sample tidal height chart (See text for explanation).

reference station.

The Tidal Current Coamplitude Chart shows the variation in mean maximum current speeds throughout the waterway. The charts reflect the effects of channels, shoals, and other bathymetric features, and show the locations with the highest or lowest current speeds. The Cophase Chart shows the variation in times of maximum flood current throughout the waterway. All times are in hours after the time of high water at the reference station.

The atlas also includes five years of daily predictions of high and low waters at one reference station location in the waterway. In the Delaware River and Bay prototype tidal atlas, the reference station is Breakwater Harbor, Delaware, near the entrance to the bay.

4.2 Nontidal Charts

The Circulation and Water Level Forecast Atlas is also proposed to include graphical representations of the effects on

circulation and water level of wind, barometric pressure, and river discharge. Charts are being designed that should enable corrections to be made to the tide and tidal current predictions according to available wind, pressure, and river discharge information on the day of interest. In waterways where NOS real-time water level gages or current meter systems are in operation, the atlas should also provide a means to extrapolate the real-time data to other locations in the waterway. The proposed sections that will provide the means to account for meteorological and river effects are described below.

Wind-Generated Circulation Charts and Wind-Generated Water Level Charts will be a series of charts showing the expected currents and water levels generated by winds of various speeds from various directions for various durations. The graphical design of these charts is proposed to be similar to that of the tidal height and tidal current charts (Figures 1 and 2), except that each chart will represent a particular wind situation rather than a particular hour of the tidal cycle. Values on these charts will be added to values on the proper tidal height or tidal current chart to provide the total height or current.

River Discharge Water Level Charts and River Discharge Circulation Charts will provide information on the effect of river discharge on water level and currents. In some estuaries it may prove more convenient to provide the information simply on a plot such as the one in Figure 3, which shows model-produced water level curves for various river discharges in the Delaware River³. Similarly, plots may provide the simplest means to describe the effect of barometric pressure on water level and circulation.

5. METHODS FOR PRODUCING THE ATLAS

5.1 Development of the Tidal Atlas

The prototype Tidal Atlas for the Delaware River and Bay was produced using a numerical hydrodynamical model (described below). The model was forced with the mean tide across the Atlantic entrance to the bay. This mean tide was determined from 18.6 years of predictions based on accurate harmonic constants determined from the least squares harmonic analysis of a year of water level data from both sides of the entrance. The model thus directly computes the water levels and currents for a mean tidal cycle; this eliminates the need to carry out analyses on time series data from thousands of

Figure 3. Example of model-produced water levels for six different river flows at the head of the tide just north of Trenton. U is a dimensionless river flow; a $U=1$ corresponds approximately to 10,000 ft³/sec discharge. All water level values are plotted relative to the tidal amplitude at the entrance to the bay, which is approximately 2.3 feet.

grid points. During the model run, times and magnitudes of high and low waters and maximum flood and ebb currents are computed for use in constructing corange, coamplitude, and cotidal charts.

The model results are then used by graphics software written on the Cyber 180/855 at the National Bureau of Standards (NBS). This software makes use of the NCAR (National Center for Atmospheric Research) graphics package and produces publication-quality charts and plots on a Dicomed DI48CR Film Processor. The contours for tidal heights, corange lines, and cotidal lines are produced using the contour routines in the NCAR package. Ranges, current amplitudes, and times of high and low waters and maximum flood and ebb, calculated during the model run, are also contoured.

5.2 Model Description

The numerical hydrodynamic model used to produce the prototype Delaware River and Bay tidal atlas is a two-dimensional version of the full three-dimensional model developed by Blumberg and Mellor⁴. The model was installed, enhanced, and evaluated by NOS on a Cyber 205 at the Department of Commerce's Consolidated Scientific Computers System at NBS. Additional enhancements were made by NOS to allow model results to be transferred to the Circulation Program Model Data Base System, and to produce the special model results presented in the atlas. The model is a programmed system of equations which computes water levels and current velocities on a 50 x 83 grid of equally spaced squares (Figure 4), each of which represents a one square kilometer region of the bay. The system of equations is expressed two-dimensionally in the area from the Atlantic Ocean

entrance between Cape Henlopen and Cape May, to the vicinity of Artificial Island. The current velocities calculated in this region are for a representative current averaged over the depth at each square. The equations are expressed one-dimensionally from Artificial Island up the river to Trenton. The current velocities calculated in this region are averaged over the channel cross section.

The model requires specific input data in order to generate water level and circulation values. This includes shoreline and depth data from NOAA nautical charts and water level data at the Atlantic Ocean entrance. For the prototype tidal atlas, the entrance data consisted of tidal heights throughout an average tidal cycle. The model can also use wind and river discharge data to simulate various meteorological conditions. The results from such model simulations will be used to produce charts representing these nontidal effects (see below).

A statistical analysis was performed to determine the accuracy of the model-generated tides and tidal currents. Predictions based on traditional NOS harmonic analysis techniques were made at 18 locations, using data obtained from an extensive NOS Delaware River and Bay circulation survey. These predictions were compared to model predictions obtained with the model being forced at the entrance with only tide predictions. The analysis involved comparison of the magnitudes and times of high water, low water, maximum flood, and maximum ebb.

5.3 Development of a Nontidal Atlas

The production of charts and plots depicting the effects of the wind on the water level and circulation of a waterway is a more difficult problem than the production of similar tidal charts. The approach presently being taken with the prototype Nontidal Atlas for the Delaware River and Bay is briefly described below.

The production of wind-generated water level and circulations charts is not simply a matter of running the numerical hydrodynamic model with various wind forcings. Various data analyses indicate that the largest changes in wind-induced water level result not from wind blowing over the Delaware Bay itself but from wind blowing over the shallow continental shelf outside the bay entrance. The numerical model of the Delaware River and Bay is forced at the Atlantic entrance, yet as just mentioned, significant wind-generated water level changes within the bay are generated outside the regime of the model.

Figure 4. Chart showing model grid system.

There are two solutions to this problem. The first is to extend the model out to include a portion of the shelf, a more difficult modeling problem because of the open boundary conditions. The second is to force the model at the entrance with nontidal water level changes that would be produced by winds over the shelf for each situation being simulated. The second choice will be used for the Delaware Bay prototype nontidal atlas. Various statistical/time series analyses are being carried out to describe the correlation between wind and nontidal water level changes at the Delaware Bay entrance.

The model will also be run with different river discharges. In the Delaware River increased river runoff raises the water level; the highest values occur nearest to Trenton (Figure 3). Increasing basin width decreases the effect of river discharge south of Artificial Island.

Barometric pressure can also change water levels, raising the water level under a low pressure center and lowering it under a high pressure center. This can be directly included in the model, but may be treated separately.

6. SUMMARY

Model-generated products such as the Circulation and Water Level Forecast Atlas should provide a means of improving on traditional tide and tidal prediction products by accounting for meteorological effects and by providing better spatial coverage in the waterway of interest.

7. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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8. REFERENCES

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